

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN GRAIN MARKET REGULATION

Taghiyeva G.,
head teacher
Babayeva S.
Hasanova Kh.
Yakubzadeh S.
assistant

Azerbaijan State Agrarian University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8388723>

Abstract

The article examines the current situation in the grain market, and also analyzes the experience of foreign countries in regulating this market. Major grain producing countries are shown to implement market interventions to avoid compromising food security. In most foreign countries, a protectionist policy is implemented to ensure food safety, to prevent the harmful influence of foreign commodity producers, and to protect the local food market. At the same time, in order to stimulate the expansion of production, extensive state aid is implemented. On the other hand, in a number of countries of the world, the problem of state control over the quality of grain, the efficient use of grain and its processing products is given an important place and importance, which is reflected in the relevant legislative acts.

Keywords: grain market, food security, development, price, production, consumption, export.

It should be noted that the price of wheat has risen to a record level in the last year, and the grain crisis is felt all over the world. Due to the increase in demand for wheat worldwide, the decrease in supply forced the increase in prices. The main factors affecting the increase in the price of wheat in the world market include unfavorable weather conditions, protectionist policy, the policy of increasing wheat reserves, the increase in variable costs, the fear of crisis and war. The global food market, affected by the weather and the novel coronavirus (COVID-19) epidemic, has been hit again by the Russia-Ukraine war and Western sanctions against Moscow. The aim of the article is to review the current state of affairs in the grain market and analyze the experience of a number of foreign countries on market regulation.

Although a downward trend was observed in the price of wheat exported from Russia from December 2021, the price increased sharply in March 2022. In June 2022, the export price of 1 ton of wheat increased by 5.04 percent compared to the previous month and reached USD 423.3. In June 2022, the maximum price of 1 ton of wheat in the Black Sea ports was 425 dollars, the minimum price was 420 dollars, and in the ports of the Sea of Azov it was 395 dollars and 390 dollars, respectively [9].

In general, factors affecting prices in the food market are complex. Thus, weather conditions, trade policy, agricultural policy, grain reserve policy, biofuel policy and changing international financial conditions are important factors affecting food prices. Due to the increase in demand for wheat worldwide, the decrease in supply is forcing the price to increase. The main factors affecting the increase in the price of wheat in the world market include unfavorable weather conditions, protectionist policy, the policy of increasing wheat re-

serves, the increase of variable costs, crises and conflicts. Another important reason is that some countries' expectations for 2022 are not optimistic. That's why China, another major wheat producer, has started seriously stockpiling wheat in recent months. According to statistics, China's wheat imports increased by 50 percent in the first half of 2021 compared to the same period of the previous year. By mid-2022, China will own 51 percent of the world's wheat reserves, according to data from the US Department of Agriculture. Such tendencies are also observed in some developed countries. In addition, domestically, the Chinese government offers farmers a minimum price for their produce, which they then supply to supplement food supplies. The Chinese government raised the minimum wheat price for the first time since 2014 in March 2021, sending bullish signals to both domestic and foreign markets [8].

Agriculture is very sensitive to climate change and extreme weather conditions. During the past year, the drought and high temperatures observed in the USA, Canada and Russia have seriously affected wheat production. For example, in the United States, drought and high temperatures caused a 40 percent decrease in the spring wheat harvest and a 10 percent decrease in the total wheat harvest in 2021 [8].

According to statistics, the largest wheat production in the 2020/21 season, 134.3 million tons, falls to China. With the production of 107.9 million tons of wheat, India ranks second in the world, and Russia ranks third with the production volume of 85.4 million tons. In general, the order of the top ten countries producing the most wheat was as follows: 4. USA - 49.7 million tons; 5. Canada - 35.2 million tons; 6. Australia - 33 million tons; 7. France - 30.5 million tons; 8. Ukraine - 25.5 million tons; 9. Pakistan - 25.2 million tons; 10. Germany - 22.1 million tons [7].

As it is known, 29 percent of wheat exports in the world are accounted for by Russia and Ukraine. For this reason, the Russia-Ukraine conflict at the beginning of the year created the basis for a rapid increase in the price of wheat on the world market. Also, in recent years, global climate change and abnormal weather conditions have a negative impact on wheat production in a number of countries, which is a factor that causes price increases.

Main directions of grain market regulation.

Major grain producing countries intervene in the market in order not to risk food security. For example, Russia has a policy of restricting wheat exports. So, from the middle of 2021, Russia began to impose a tax on wheat exports. On the other hand, it applies a wheat export quota to regulate exports.

The experience of foreign countries shows that the government prefers targeted support to producers in the agricultural sector and the implementation of protectionist measures. Thus, 25% of the income of farmers in the USA, 40% in Canada, 50% in the countries of the European Union, and more than 70% in Japan are state subsidies. Such a policy is implemented in many countries that are trying to ensure their own food security, prevent the harmful influence of foreign commodity producers, and defend the local food market.

One of the main directions here is influencing the producers by subsidizing the prices of their products. At the same time, the main differences in that case are only in the size, structure and forms of financing. For example, 38-39% of prices in the European Union countries, 36-37% in the USA, 30-31% in Canada and 6-7% in Australia are covered by subsidies.

In countries aiming to solve the problem of self-sufficiency with important food products, including grain products, the share of state aid to agriculture in the value of the sold product is at the level of 50-70%. At present, one of the serious problems in grain farms in most of the world's countries is related to compensation of damage, and this issue is directly regulated by insurance relations. Thus, positive experience in insurance relations has been collected in developed countries.

It should be noted that in a number of countries of the world, the problem of state control over the quality of grain, the rational use of grain and its processing products is given an important place and importance, which is reflected in the relevant legislative acts. Legislative documents regulate relations in the field of grain production and are aimed at solving a number of issues: regulating the rules of grain production, processing and storage; determination and provision of grain quality standards; setting fixed rates for grain transportation services.

One of the important conditions for stabilization and regulation of the grain market in the world, and for coordination, is the preparation of the mechanisms of cooperation of the world countries on grain at the international level in accordance with global challenges. In this direction, the International Grains Council located in London operates and this Council includes 23 countries. The main goal of the council is international co-

operation on stabilizing the world grain market. In Turkey, which is at the level of strategic cooperation with Azerbaijan, serious importance is attached to the production of grain products and the creation of reserves. The State Grain Agency of Turkey coordinates and regulates these issues in the country. The agency's strategic task is to maintain stability in the domestic grain products market, ensure balance, organize grain interventions if necessary, etc. consists of. In recent years, on average, 20 million tons of wheat have been produced in Turkey, and the demand for this important food product is 17-18 million tons. Despite the fact that production exceeds consumption in the country, an average of 4 million tons of wheat is imported every year. This allows strengthening the reserves of wheat, which is an important and strategic food product. The Russian Federation, a neighbor of our country and a strategic foreign trade partner in the non-oil sector of Azerbaijan, is one of the world's leading producers of grain products. Strategic problems of grain products in Russia, including efficiency issues, regulatory mechanisms are implemented by the Ministry of Agriculture of Russia. The volume of grain export in this country is increasing, including its price.

Another country with strategic trade and economic relations with Azerbaijan - Kazakhstan is also known as a grain country. Part of the grain import required for the formation of the grain reserve of our country - mainly wheat import - is related to Kazakhstan[2]. However, in recent years, Kazakhstan's position in the world grain market has weakened somewhat, and Russia's activation is the main factor in this. The total volume of grain production in the country is 18 million tons per year.

It should be noted that in order to increase the efficiency of the grain products market, it is important to pay special attention to a number of issues at the micro level. Analysis of the external and internal environment - microenvironment and macroenvironment factors, study of competitors - detection of competitors, assessment of their strategy and purpose, number and potential opportunities, weak and strong aspects are also included in the analysis direction of management. From the point of view of these factors, special attention is paid to defining and forecasting market demand, selecting market segments, substantiating the strategy of differentiation and forecasting of offers, analyzing the potential competitive environment, identifying potential competitive advantages, and determining access to foreign markets.

References:

1. About world grain reserves and other tools for solving the problem of instability of grain markets. FAO Investment Center. <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i3338r.pdf>
2. Kazakhstan has increased its supply of wheat to foreign markets. <https://kapital.kz/economic/73871/kazakhstan-narastil-postavki-pshenitsyna-vneshniye-rynki.html>
3. World wheat consumption will overtake production in 2019. <http://www.ukragroconsult.com>

4. The top three world grain exporters are Russia, the USA and Canada. <https://www.agroxxi.ru/mirovye-agronovosti/troika-mirovyh-yeksporterov-zernovyh-rossija-ssha-i-kanada.html>

5. Kuksin S.V. State and prospects for the development of the Russian wheat market as an integral part of the world grain market // Vestnik NGIEI. 2018. No. 5 (84). <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/sostoyanie-i-perspektivy-razvitiya-rynka-pshenitsy-rossii-kak-sostavnoy-chasti-mirovogo-rynka-zerna>

6. Canada will harvest its lowest wheat harvest in three years. <http://agroportal.ua/news/mir/kanada-soberet-samyi-nizkii-za-tri-goda-urozhai-pshenitsy>

7. <https://latifundist.com/en/rating/top-10-stran-proizvoditelej-pshenitsy-v-202021-mg>

8. https://azertag.az/xeber/Qlobal_bugda_bohrani_ve_Azerbaycana_tesirleri-1969845

9. <https://www.apk-inform.com/en/prices>